

NEUROBIOLOGY

NUROMYELITIS OPTICA SPECTRUM DISORDER-ASSOCIATED COGNITIVE CHANGES – BRIEF REVIEW

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Abstract

Neuromyelitis optica (NMOSD) is a relatively rare demyelinating chronic disease of the central nervous system. The key features of NMOSD are optic neuritis, myelitis and brainstem syndromes (mostly area postrema syndrome). The aim of our study was to discuss the Cognitive impairments (CI) in NMOSD – the reported frequency, factors associated with CI, types of CI and the prognosis.

Results: The prevalence of CI among NMOSD patients is 30-70%. The most impaired cognitive domains are executive functioning and memory, although several cases with aphasia, apraxia and agnosia were also reported. The factors associated with CI as well as the pathogenesis of them are poorly understood. CI can be relapse and non-relapse associated.

Conclusions: CI is very often in cases with NMOSD. Despite this, the pathogenesis and their course are poorly understood. CI impact the quality of life and independence of NMOSD patients. Cognitive rehabilitation is recommended in broad treatment program for such cases.

Keywords: Neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder, cognitive impairments.

Neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorder (NMOSD) is a relatively rare demyelinating relapsing chronic disease of the central nervous system that predominantly affects spinal cord, brainstem and optic nerve (Oertel, 2019; Aljarallah, 2025; Yazdan Panah, 2026). It affects all age groups with strong female predominance (Apiraksattayakul, 2024).

Although the key clinical manifestations of NMOSD include optic neuritis, myelitis and brainstem signs (more often area postrema syndrome), new studies are focused on increasing prevalence of multidomain cognitive impairment (CI) among these patients (Yazdan Panah, 2026).

The reported prevalence of CI among NMOSD patients is 30-70%, depending on study methodology, neuropsychology battery used, the age of the study sample and comorbidities (Czarnecka, 2020; Apiraksattayakul, 2024).

Factors, associated with CI in NMOSD. The factors, associated with CI are poorly understood. Possibly CI may occur in early stages of the disease and may worsen with its progression and the number of relapses (Czarnecka, 2020; Valdivia-Tangarife, 2025), although new studies show no association between the duration of the disease, number of relapses or the presence of aquaporin 4 antibodies and the CI (Apiraksattayakul, 2024). However, the severity of the disease, measured by Expanded Disability Status Scale (EDSS) scoring is strongly associated with the development of CI (Kazzi, 2024; Apiraksattayakul, 2024). Poor cognitive functioning might be also associated with late-onset NMOSD (Kazzi, 2024), but recent meta-analysis rejects such association (Apiraksattayakul, 2024). There are no statistically significant associations between NMOSD - CI and gender (Kazzi, 2024; Apiraksattayakul, 2024). Patients with low formal education level

show higher prevalence of CI (Czarnecka, 2020; Apiraksattayakul, 2024; Kazzi, 2024; Valdivia-Tangarife, 2025). Moreover, cognitive dysfunctions in pediatric onset NMOSD may impact long-term academic outcomes of such children leading to low formal education and additional CI (Deiva, 2020; Kazzi, 2024). The link between depression and CI in cases with NMOSD is questionable (Oertel, 2019; Apiraksattayakul, 2024; Kazzi, 2024), although severe depression could independently lead to CI (Czarnecka, 2020; Kazzi, 2024).

Associations between CI and cerebral structural changes. About 80% of anti-aquaporin 4 positive patients have cerebral lesions at aquaporin 4 rich zones, that play important role for cognitive functioning such as hypothalamus and periependymal zones (Oertel, 2019). Patients with Myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein antibody-associated disease (MOGAD) also show alterations at zones, associated with cognitive functioning (Rust, 2026). However, the link between CI and cerebral changes in cases with NMOSD is not well understood (Oertel, 2019; Czarnecka, 2020). CI might be associated with lesions at right parietal lobe, left frontal and parietal lobes and with medial cortical and hippocampal atrophy (Apiraksattayakul, 2024), grey matter atrophy of frontal and temporal lobe, insula, thalamus and hippocampus and white matter fiber disruption at corona radiata and optic radiation (Rust, 2026).

Associations between CI and neurotransmitters dysregulation. NMOSD leads to astrocytopathy with secondary neurodegeneration in particular cognitive related brain zones. Moreover, this leads to neurotransmitter changes with glutamate excitation and decrease of gamma-butyric acid levels in specific brain zones (Oertel, 2019; Zhao, 2024). CI in NMOSD correlates also with diminished functional connectivity between

different brain zones (mostly posterior default mode network and salience network and the anterior wedge and superior temporal gyrus) (Zhao, 2024).

Altered cognitive domains in NMOSD

According to Apiraksattayakul et al. (2024) the significance of cognitive complaints in cases with NMOSD depends on who have reported them. Their study (Apiraksattayakul, 2024) showed that “Montreal Cognitive Assessment [MoCA] scores of patients were significantly lower when their relatives reported the patient’s cognitive problems, regardless of whether the patients themselves reported cognitive issues”. Subjective complaints of cognitive dysfunctions doesn’t correlate with the severity of CI (Oertel, 2019; Czarnecka, 2020; Apiraksattayakul, 2024; Rust, 2026). However, screening tools for global cognitive functioning such as Mini Mental State Examination and MoCA underestimate cognitive dysfunctions in cases with NMOSD (Andrao, 2025). This is because such tools are developed for patients with degenerative dementias primary for patients with degenerative dementias, which have different clinical and neuropsychological profile.

Kong et al. (2022) suggested four different cognitive profiles in cases with NMOSD – preserved cognition (30.3%), mild attention changes (31.8%), mild multidomain (27.3%) and severe multidomain CI (10.6%). The last group showed the most prominent decline at Paced Auditory Serial Addition Test.

The most frequently affected cognitive domain in NMOSD is executive functioning (Kong, 2022; Apiraksattayakul, 2024; Andrao, 2025). Executive functions are a group of high cortical functions that regulate behavior, problem solving and thinking. The basic executive functions are cognitive inhibition and interference control (selective attention), working memory and cognitive flexibility (Diamond, 2012). Of them, the most impaired in cases with NMOSD are attention, working memory and processing speed (Oertel, 2019; Kong, 2022; Apiraksattayakul, 2024; Kazzi, 2024; Andrao, 2025).

The second most frequently affected cognitive domain in NMOSD is memory. Patients with NMOSD may have difficulties in episodic memory, short-term memory, verbal memory and the retrieval of memory (Oertel, 2019; Apiraksattayakul, 2024).

Language changes are less often in cases with NMOSD, despite this some patients developed language processing difficulties (Sawada, 2014; Lopes, 2025; Yazdan Panah, 2026), which along with impaired cognitive speed might lead to specific semantic aphasia. Few cases with motor aphasia are also published in literature (Ikeda, 2011; Matsusue, 2016; Furukawa, 2017).

Agnosia is very rare in cases with NMOSD, although some cases with finger agnosia are described (Ikeda, 2011; Matsusue, 2016).

Apraxia is also a rare condition in NMOSD (Sawada, 2014). Shozawa et al. (2018) described a case with diagnostic apraxia in 48 years old women with NMOSD and corpus callosal disconnection syndrome.

Course of CI in NMOSD.

The course of CI in NMOSD is currently unclear. Some specific CI can be relapse related or could even improve with treatment (Czarnecka, 2020; Saab, 2022;

Kazzi, 2024). Despite this, in most of the cases the development of CI is not associated with the number of relapses and don’t improve with classical NMOSD treatment (Oertel, 2019; Czarnecka, 2020; Apiraksattayakul, 2024; Kazzi, 2024; Yazdan Panah, 2026). Moreover, some patients with CI have relatively low other kind of disability (Czarnecka, 2020; Kazzi, 2024). CI is rarely developed within the first 3 years after the disease onset (Czarnecka, 2020). On the other hand, some patients with long duration doesn’t develop CI at all (Czarnecka, 2020; Kong, 2022; Apiraksattayakul, 2024). However, with the transmitter imbalance and increased disconnection, CI might progress over time (Zhao, 2024), leading to additionally impairment of quality of life and self-independency of NMOSD patients.

There is no currently developed treatment against CI in NMOSD, although some medications against glutamatergic excitotoxicity and cholinesterase inhibitors might be used, although with unclear outcome. The cognitive rehabilitation is strongly recommended (Valdivia-Tangarife, 2025).

Conclusions: CI is very often in cases with NMOSD. Despite this, the pathogenesis and its course are poorly understood. The most impaired cognitive domains are executive functioning (selective attention, cognitive flexibility and working memory) and memory, however several cases with aphasia, agnosia and apraxia are also described. There are four described profiles NMOSD patients regarding cognitive functioning – with preserved cognition, with mild attention deficits, with mild multimodal and with severe multimodal CI. CI could be relapse or non-relapse related. There is no currently discovered treatment against CI in NMOSD, although cognitive rehabilitation is recommended.

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